

Call for papers

International Journal of Electromagnetics invites high quality manuscripts in the research areas of electromagnetic modeling, analysis and implementation. The journal proposes to stimulate the development of latest technology in industry and academia. Good quality review papers and short communications are also acceptable.

Topics

- Electric Power Line
- Electrical Machine
- Electromagnetic Breaker
- Electromagnetic Communication
- Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC)
- Electromagnetic Devices
- Electromagnetic Field Theory
- Electromagnetic Interferences (EMI)
- Electromagnetic Inverse Problems
- Electromagnetic Launch
- Electromagnetic Material Modeling
- Electromagnetic Measurement Technology and Instruments
- Electromagnetic Metamaterials
- Electromagnetic Nondestructive Testing
- Electromagnetic Numerical Analysis
- Electromagnetic Physics
- Electromagnetic Propagation in Microstrip lines
- Electromagnetic Solid Mechanics
- Electromagnetic Structure Optimization
- Electromagnetic Study in Antennas
- Electromagnetism and Medical Devices
- Electromagnetism in Medical Research
- Electromyography
- Interconnects
- Magnetic Fluid
- Novel Materials for Transmission lines
- On-Chip and Off-Chip EMC
- Optics
- Transmission Lines

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-Mail: journalijel@airccse.com or through [Submission System](#). Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : June 25, 2022**
- Notification : July 25, 2022
- Final Manuscript Due : August 01, 2022
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact us: ije_ljournal@yahoo.com or journalijel@airccse.com

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